

Preparation and Characterisation of Complexes of Bis- π -cyclopentadienyl and Bis- π -indenyl Molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride with Mercaptotriazoles

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Manuscript received 21 November 1981, revised 26 November 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

The reactions of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride and bis- π -indenyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (HAFT), 4-benzylidene-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (HBFT) and 4-salicylidene-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (H_2SFT) have been studied in dry benzene. The products isolated have been characterised by elemental analyses, electrical conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements, and IR, electronic and 1H nmr spectral data. The ligands HAFT and HBFT act as NS^- bidentate, whereas H_2SFT acts as $NS-O^-$ tridentate chelating agent.

THE transition metal complexes of NS and NSO donors have been known for quite sometime, but an increasing number of such complexes have been studied in recent years¹⁻¹². One interesting class of compounds containing such donors is the mercaptotriazoles. However, no such study has been done to know complexing behaviour of such type of ligands towards π -metalloenedihalide. In this paper, the synthesis and characterisation of complexes of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl-molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride and bis- π -indenyl-molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (HAFT), 4-benzylidene-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (HBFT) and 4-salicylidene-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (H_2SFT) are reported.

Experimental

Materials: Bis- π -cyclopentadienyl-molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride and bis- π -indenyl-molybde-

num(VI)-oxo-dichloride were prepared by the method reported in the literature^{13,14}. The ligands were prepared by the reported method¹⁵. Benzene was dried over sodium wire. Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture and all operations were carried out under anhydrous condition.

Preparation of complexes: All the complexes were prepared by a general procedure described briefly below.

The appropriate mercaptotriazole (1 mol) was added to a solution of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl-molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride or bis- π -indenyl-molybdenum(VI)-oxo-dichloride (1 mol) in dry benzene (~50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed. Evolution of hydrogen chloride began after 0.5 h. The refluxing was continued until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased (8-10 h.). The resulting mixture was then evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The products were repeatedly washed with ethanol and petroleum ether to remove traces of the ligand and the metal salt. The complexes were crystallised from a mixture of nitromethane/diethylether (1:1). The purity of the compounds were checked by tlc. The elemental analyses correspond to the stoichiometry, $R_2MoO(L)Cl$ or $R_2MoO(L)$ (where, $R = \pi-C_5H_5$ or $\pi-C_9H_7$; $L = HAFT$ or $HBFT$; $L' = H_2SFT$).

Characterisation of complexes:

Molybdenum was estimated as 8-hydroxyquinolate. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate and chlorine as silver chloride. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were carried out at Central Drug and Research Institute, Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility at room temperature on powdered complexes were measured on a standard Gouy balance. Mercury(II)-tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) ($x = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. units at 293 K) was used as calibrant. Electrolytic conductance measurements were carried out in nitromethane on a Beckmann

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						λ_{\max} cm ⁻¹
	C	H	N	S	M	Cl	
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(AFT)Cl	83.6 (83.8)	2.6 (2.6)	12.1 (12.2)	6.7 (6.9)	20.8 (20.8)	7.6 (7.7)	35200-35600
(π -C ₆ H ₇) ₂ MoO(AFT)Cl	44.9 (44.9)	2.6 (2.8)	9.8 (9.9)	5.6 (5.7)	17.1 (17.1)	6.2 (6.3)	35400-35700
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(BFT)Cl	43.5 (43.7)	2.8 (2.9)	10.0 (10.2)	5.8 (5.8)	17.4 (17.5)	6.8 (6.4)	32000-34400
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(BFT)Cl	51.6 (51.8)	3.0 (3.0)	8.4 (8.6)	4.6 (4.7)	14.7 (14.8)	5.3 (5.4)	32300-34600
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(SFT)	45.3 (45.4)	2.8 (2.8)	10.5 (10.6)	5.9 (6.0)	18.0 (18.2)	—	32800-34980
(π -C ₆ H ₇) ₂ MoO(SFT)	58.4 (58.5)	2.9 (3.0)	8.8 (8.9)	5.1 (5.1)	15.8 (15.8)	—	32700-35200

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS

Compd.	ν_{N-H}	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{\text{thio-}}^{\text{amide-IV}}$	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-S}	ν_{M-N}
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(AFT)Cl	3120m	—	740m	980s	360w	480w
(π -C ₆ H ₇) ₂ MoO(AFT)Cl	3080	—	740m	980s	380w	435w
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(BFT)Cl	—	1610s	760m	970s	360w	440w
(π -C ₆ H ₇) ₂ MoO(BFT)Cl	—	1615m	755m	970s	375w	480w
(π -C ₆ H ₅) ₂ MoO(SFT)	—	1605s	740m	980s	370w	540w
(π -C ₆ H ₇) ₂ MoO(SFT)	—	1605s	740m	985s	370w	450w

RC-18A conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (benzene) on a Perkin-Elmer 4000A and a Cary-14 spectrophotometers. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at a sweep width of 300 Hz.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are found to be soluble in nitromethane, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide, and moderately soluble in benzene, dichloromethane and tetrahydrofuran. The solutions of the complexes are susceptible to hydrolysis. The electrolytic conductance of the complexes in nitromethane are consistent with their non-electrolytic nature.

Magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra : The magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate the diamagnetic nature of the complexes. The electronic spectra of HBFT and H₂SFT show two bands at 32500-32200 and 34800-35300 cm⁻¹, whereas only one broad band is observed at 35200-35800 cm⁻¹ in the ligand HAFT. These bands may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the azomethine linkage. On complexation, these bands move slightly to lower energy in HBFT and H₂SFT complexes, which may be due to the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to metal atom as reported¹⁶. However, in HAFT complexes the band appears exactly at the same position as in the ligand.

Infrared spectra : The important ir bands and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2.

These ligands contain H-N-C=S grouping and can undergo, thione \rightleftharpoons thiol tautomerism. The spectra of the ligands show four bands at 1560-1550, 1250, 1090-1080 and 790-780 cm⁻¹ which are assigned^{17,18} to thioamide-I, -II, -III and -IV vibrations, respectively. These bands are not pure and have contributions¹⁹ from δ_{N-H} , $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=S}$ and δ_{C-H} . The thioamide-IV band has been found to have maximum $\nu_{C=S}$ contribution¹⁸. In the complexes, this band shifts to lower frequency (~ 40 -30 cm⁻¹) suggesting^{17,20} the coordination of the sulphur atom to metal. A weak band at 2500-2480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ligands suggest the presence of SH group. The conspicuous absence of the ν_{S-H} band in the spectra of all complexes confirms the bonding through sulphur after deprotonation.

Strong bands observed in the ligands HBFT around 1630 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$. In the spectra of complexes this band shifts to lower frequency (~ 25 cm⁻¹) indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to metal atom. Their ir band at 3200-3100 cm⁻¹ in the ligand HAFT due to ν_{N-H} of the primary amino group is shifted towards the lower wave number (~ 60 -50 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of complexes, indicating the coordination of the amino nitrogen to the metal atom. In addition, the ligand H₂SFT also shows one band at ~ 3400 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν_{OH} of phenolic group. However, in the spectra of the complexes of H₂SFT, this band disappears indicating the coordination of the phenolic oxygen to the metal atom through deprotonation.

In the spectra of bis- π -cyclopentadienyl-molybdenum(VI) derivatives, the presence of C₆H₅

ring is inferred²¹ by the absorption bands at ~ 2900 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching), ~ 1150 - 1140 and 1025 cm^{-1} (C-H in-plane deformation). Sharp and strong absorption bands at 1460 - 1440 cm^{-1} indicate the C-C stretching (asymmetric ring breathing), and also π -bonding of the ring with the molybdenum oxo-group. The presence of indenyl group is indicated by the usual peaks due to C_8H_7^- ring. The bands due to phenyl part of the indenyl group appeared at 1670 and 1450 (C-C stretching), 1380 and 750 cm^{-1} (C-H in-plane and out-of-plane deformations, respectively). A band at 710 cm^{-1} may be due to the methylene rocking vibration (since indene itself shows a band at ~ 700 cm^{-1}). Davison and Rakita²² have pointed out that near 3000 cm^{-1} , $\eta^5\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8$ or $\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7$ should show only one band in the ir spectra, whereas $\eta^1\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8$ or $\eta^1\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7$ and $\eta^3\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8$ or $\eta^3\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7$ should show four and three bands, respectively because of lower symmetry. In our complexes, the presence of single band at ~ 2900 cm^{-1} indicates the pentahapto nature of cyclopentadienyl ring. In addition, a very sharp band at ~ 980 cm^{-1} in all the complexes is due to $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ stretching frequency²¹.

¹H nmr spectra : The ¹H nmr spectra for three complexes, $\text{R}_2\text{MoO}(\text{AFT})\text{Cl}$, $\text{R}_2\text{MoO}(\text{BFT})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{R}_2\text{MoO}(\text{SFT})$ ($\text{R}=\pi\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8$), and the ligands were recorded in deuterated dimethylformamide. The intensity of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The following conclusions may be derived by comparing the spectra of the ligands and their corresponding complexes :

(i) A signal in all triazole derivatives at δ 6.5 (ppm) may be assigned to the protons of cyclopentadienyl ring. The appearance of single, sharp resonance signal for C_8H_7^- protons indicate rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis.

(ii) The signal due to SH proton appears at about δ 4.4 in the ligands which disappears in the corresponding complexes, indicating the deprotonation of thiol proton.

(iii) The proton signal observed at δ 9.8 in the ligand H_2SFT may be due to phenolic proton. This signal disappears in the complexes indicating the deprotonation of the phenolic group.

Thus, on the basis of the above discussion, it appears that ligands HAFT and HBFT act as a NS bidentate chelating agent coordinating *via* thiol sulphur and amino nitrogen (in HAFT) or azomethine nitrogen (in HBFT), whereas H_2SFT acts as a ONS tridentate chelating agent having coordination sites at thiol sulphur, azomethine nitrogen and phenolic

oxygen. Therefore, on the basis of these studies, the following structures have been assigned to different complexes.

where, represents the anion of the ligands

HAFT and HBFT and represents anion of the ligand H_2SFT ; $\text{R}=\pi\text{-C}_8\text{H}_8$ or $\pi\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7$.

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